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Adapting Digital Change in Higher Education Institutions: A Case Study

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Abstract:

Higher education institutions are going through a dramatic change due to the quick development of digital technology, necessitating institutions to adjust to new approaches to instruction, management, and student involvement. When change occurs in any organization, people undergo an adaptation process; structural transformation happens. This paper is a case study of a higher education institution examining how a university adapts to change due to digital transformation. It also suggests a change theory explaining its appropriateness in the current situation. The study focuses on the present situation of the university, which describes enterprise resource planning software adaptation and its effect on the institution. Two 'change leaders' opinions have been stated, revealing the reality of the change environment. This study identified inefficiencies in operations, limited functionality, slow implementation, and changing payroll processes as challenges to adapting to digital change. This paper proposed John Kotter's 8-step change model as a change strategy because it provides a clear, structured framework for leading successful organizational change in a vast transformation.

Keywords: Digital change, leadership, adaptation

1. Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving educational landscape, higher educational institutions face constant challenges in maintaining efficient and effective administrative processes (Kotter et al., 2012). One such challenge is the management of personnel actions within the Human Resources (HR) department. Many organizations have outdated or inefficient processes for managing personnel and payroll. At the University, the reliance on manual, paper-based Personnel Action Forms (PAFs) has led to inefficiencies, delays, and errors, affecting payroll accuracy and data reporting. Lost forms, data-entry delays, and payroll inaccuracies are a constant struggle for faculty and staff. These kinds of problems lower the trust between the faculty and the Administration. It also reduces morale and efficiency at the University. With the increasing demand for streamlined operations, senior leadership has recognized the need for an electronic solution. This paper describes a higher education institution's transition to an electronic Personnel Action Form (ePAF) system, the benefits it offers, and the steps involved in its development and implementation.

2. Background

A higher education institution in the southeastern USA is transitioning from a paper-based file system to an electronic personnel action form (ePAF) system. Currently, the University utilizes 'Peoplesoft' as its 'Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system'. All university faculty and staff are impacted by this change process in implementing the organization's electronic personnel action forms (ePAF) system. Before the ePAF project began, personnel actions such as hiring, terminating, giving a raise, transferring, or even changing a supervisor were handled by completing a paper 'Personnel Action Form (PAF)'. This paper form was initially completed by hand and then sent to the human resources (HR) department via interdepartmental mail. However, in recent years, they were able to transition to scanning the form in as a

PDF and emailing it to the human resource department who then printed it out to make notes on, entered the data into the HR tables, and then passed along stacks of papers to the Office of Fiscal Planning and Analysis (OFPA) or the Office of Research Administration (ORA) depending on how the employee is funded. This system was still not very efficient. PAFs are regularly lost or delayed, which results in payroll errors and invalid data reporting.

For all these reasons, Senior Leadership has prioritized creating an electronic version of the form or ePAF. This is currently being developed and implemented in phases. Initially, the entire project was supposed to fit within an 18-month timeline, but there have been several severe delays, and the project has been in development for 27 months. One reason for the delay is the lack of resources. Due to funding limitations, the University has not purchased every module of PeopleSoft. Instead, an in-house team of developers is working with the PeopleSoft modules to develop and customize them as per the requirements of the University.

This transformation will primarily occur in the university's HR office but will impact departmental offices across campus. In this new process, departments enter the data directly into the system. It is then moved through the proper workflow channels for approval before reaching HR, who will ultimately approve and then run a process to load the information from the form into the tables. The transition from data entry to data review has been challenging. However, the HR Assistant Operations Manager, Emily Miller (not the real name), believes the change will benefit her team and the University.

Emily's primary team consists of two operations specialists who are responsible for entering almost all PAF data for the university. This means that only two people are entering most of the employment data for almost 6,000 employees. There may be higher volume at certain times of the year, but these individuals enter data constantly. The demand can get so overwhelming that they must pull other HR employees away from their jobs in benefits or employee relations to assist with data entry. With such a large volume of entries, there are bound to be things that fall through the cracks and get entered incorrectly or even missed altogether.

Emily shared that phase one of the ePAF project centered on all employee terminations and has been completed. Phase 2 involves hiring and rehiring and is being rolled out in phases—the first being students, which has been implemented in production. However, due to the demand to support other areas, the development team has had to take a hiatus from working on this project.

She mentioned that the completed phases have helped with data consistency and accurate reporting and reduced payroll errors, as electronic PAFs are processed much faster than paper. However, the timeline delay has resulted in an odd transitional period where some actions are electronic, but the majority are still on paper. The Human Resources department has done everything it can to avoid confusion. However, the temporary hiatus has lasted longer than expected, and departments are anxious to know when PAFs will be entirely electronic.

There are some frustrations surrounding the delayed timeline, and the HR team and the development team are receiving pressure from senior leadership to move as quickly as possible. However, some delays are inevitable, especially when working with a small team that must maintain regular duties in addition to the project. In the case of this transformation, the operations specialists will eventually have an entirely new job description that will involve data review and customer service. The challenge is achieving the project goals as quickly as possible while maintaining the current workload. The HR department has also experienced employee turnover during the project, which poses additional challenges as several employees are still learning their responsibilities and stepping into the middle of this project. By developing this new change plan, this team's goal is to expedite this transformation and implement the project's remaining phases as quickly as possible without causing significant disruptions or additional delays.

3. Current Challenges Faced by the Organization

The University has not purchased every available module of PeopleSoft due to budgetary restrictions. This limits the functionality that can be integrated into the system, forcing the institution to rely on partial solutions that may not fully meet all its needs. The lack of access to specific modules may result in inefficiencies or the need for workarounds in various functional areas. The fact that the University has customized PeopleSoft to meet its specific needs means that the system is tailored to the institution's unique processes. While customizations can be beneficial, they create several challenges. The system is now more complex and more demanding to maintain. Custom code can break with updates or require constant modification. As the team works on custom solutions, each change requires detailed attention to ensure it aligns with the rest of the system. The development team can spend significant time on adjustments, slowing down progress.

The team may be stretched thin, working on multiple high-priority projects simultaneously. This can lead to slower implementation and delays in addressing issues or enhancing functionality. Customization requires specialized knowledge of PeopleSoft and the University's unique processes. If there is turnover or knowledge gaps within the team, it can slow project timelines and lead to inconsistent results. Due to the in-house nature of development, projects take a long time to complete. This means that even if a new system or process is designed to address inefficiencies, it may not be ready for implementation for a long period. As a result, many functional areas of the university are left using manual or outdated methods to meet their operational needs. Some business processes are still managed using traditional methods, leading departments and staff to rely on spreadsheets, paper forms, or other informal solutions. These workarounds can be inefficient, prone to errors, and lack integration with the ERP system, which further increases the overall inefficiency of the system (Sharma et al., 2020).

A senior development team member, David John (not real name), spoke to this, citing that their project list continues to grow despite this project being labelled top priority. The additional projects come from several different sources. One is employee turnover. As employees leave the University, their job duties must fall to other team members until their roles

are filled. Already, tight timelines mean that some of these duties must be given higher priority. Secondly, the current political environment is highly volatile. New executive orders and legislative changes are being authorized almost daily. These may affect the university's reporting standards or payroll processes, and such a highly customized system could take weeks to alter. These team members spoke of their frustration with the delays, but also expressed that they did not feel much could be done beyond expanding the team. However, training new people would take even more time and resources. They hope a new plan could help realign everyone's goals and interests.

As the university grows and needs change, the highly customized system may become harder to scale. Adapting the system to new requirements or future expansions may involve significant development time, extending the already long timelines. In summary, the combination of funding limitations, a highly customized system, an overstretched in-house development team, slow project implementation, and reliance on outdated workarounds presents significant barriers to the effective use of PeopleSoft. These constraints create inefficiencies and hinder the university's ability to streamline operations and improve overall productivity (Khaparde, 2012).

4. The Role of the Change Leader

Leader actions, including senior leaders' strategic choices and senior leaders' and middle managers' typical behavioral styles, have been linked with the outcomes of organizational change (Oreg & Berson, 2019). In the case of the selected university, leaders must develop a compelling vision for digital transformation, emphasizing how new technology will improve administrative and learning efficiency. They should actively include stakeholders by resolving issues, communicating clearly, and coordinating digital projects with the university's strategic objectives. The leader must provide thorough training programs, promote departmental cooperation, and honor early adopters who use digital tools to develop social motivation and personal ability. Leaders' role in adopting digital transformation in the selected university is crucial because they drive change, cultivate an innovative culture, and ensure that faculty and staff have a seamless transition. Leaders are already facing constraints in this project due to budget limitations, as it is expensive to upgrade infrastructure, buy new technology, and train employees; that is what the university is already facing. Integrating new digital tools with current systems might be difficult and require more effort and technical assistance. Moreover, there might be cybersecurity risks. Leaders must face change resistance from the faculty and staff because of the lack of expertise, hesitancy to embrace new processes, or fear of job loss. Leaders should be careful about their traits, values, and behaviors as they reflect in their followers' reactions to an organizational change; also, leaders' emphasis on stimulation and novelty will decrease their followers' intentions to resist organizational change (Oreg & Berson, 2011). Additionally, six sources of influence (personal motivation, personal ability, social motivation, social ability, structural motivation, and structural ability) will also be helpful for leaders to make lasting behavioral changes in their followers (Grenny et al., 2023). Overall, this transformation process will allow leaders to increase their expertise in adapting to digital change with improved learning experiences.

5. Change Plan Using Kotter's 8-Step Model

In today's evolving landscape, organizations are emphasizing digital transformation to survive. (Trawick & Carraher, 2023, p. 39) The selected university still uses paper forms for many HR and Payroll functions. Building a new electronic Personnel Action Form (PAF) in the Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system is essential to solving these issues. The original plan was for an 18-month rollout. However, as this deadline has now exceeded 27 months, the University needs a new structured approach to achieve these efficiencies before technology becomes obsolete. Clear structure and planning make John Kotter's (2014) 8-step change model an excellent option, providing a roadmap for change and improvement on the old paper system. It is appropriate to lead change in a big and complex environment.

5.1. Step 1: Create a Sense of Urgency

The university still uses paper forms for almost all HR data. Because of the inconsistency of manual entry and the time delays, dozens of university staff members' paychecks have not been correct, requiring more manual entries to correct mistakes on the next pay cycle or special check runs that require time and effort from both HR and Payroll. Faculty and staff must be assured that their paychecks will be accurate and that their requests will not be misplaced. By highlighting the impact on morale, productivity, and the university's reputation as a good workplace, change leaders can demonstrate the need for an effective PAF system. Building urgency compels stakeholders to engage with the change quickly, and the organization gets their buy-in, especially when they see the direct benefits of improving the process (Kotter, 2014).

5.2. Step 2: Build a Guiding Coalition

Once the urgency has been established, the next step is identifying and building a coalition. This coalition should include influential leaders and department heads across IT, finance, human resources, and the Administration who experience day-to-day administrative challenges. Coalitions thrive when composed of individuals who believe in the vision and can motivate others to join (Kotter & Rathgeber, 2016). This diverse group of change leaders will help design a plan that addresses administrative requirements and user needs.

5.3. Step 3: Form a Strategic Vision and Initiatives

The coalition will help build an accurate, reliable, user-friendly PAF system that reduces errors and misplaced paperwork based on their vision of how they want to see the PAF work. The University must be willing to implement specific initiatives, such as streamlined data-entry protocols, standardized approval workflows, and consistent reporting

procedures. These initiatives should be measurable so stakeholders can track the progress made. This initiative will help unite the organization and ensure the system works (Kotter, 2014).

5.4. Step 4: Communicate the Vision

Communication is what keeps faculty, staff, and administrators informed and engaged. The coalition will send out campus-wide emails, bulletin updates, and departmental presentations reinforcing the change they are trying to make with the new system. The coalition will also recruit ambassadors from each department. This process will help spread awareness and get buy-in from the users. The ambassadors will then train others in the new procedures while emphasizing the long-term benefits. Frequent, transparent communication reduces uncertainty, raises trust, and increases department cooperation (Kotter, 2014).

5.5. Step 5: Remove Barriers

Structural, technological, and cultural barriers often do not help organizations change. Challenges may arise with HR and IT constraints, resistance to new processes, or insufficient training. Pilot programs or “super-user” tests can identify problems early on. These users will help with real-time feedback when problems arise, and the change leaders can get immediate feedback. Providing support resources, such as an online helpdesk, ensures that problems that arise do not derail the momentum. Removing these barriers will bring a smoother adoption of the new PAF system (Kotter, 2014).

5.6. Step 6: Generate Short-Term Wins

Short-term wins help faculty and staff realize that the changes are working and will be shared University-wide. For example, reducing payroll discrepancies within a pilot department or automating time-off requests can show tangible benefits. Ensuring everyone knows about these successes through emails, newsletters, or staff meetings will keep morale high and encourage departments that have not yet transitioned to commit to the new process (Kotter & Rathgeber, 2016).

5.7. Step 7: Sustain Acceleration

With initial successes achieved, the coalition must continue its effort to go on board with additional departments. The guiding change leaders must continue monitoring progress, refining procedures, and celebrating improvements. Complacency can set in once early goals are met. For momentum to stay strong, the end goal of a fully functional, error-free payroll and HR system must be reinforced (Kotter, 2014).

5.8. Step 8: Institute Change

Finally, for this change to work, everyone will have to use it. Instead of a “That is not how we do it here,” it must be an attitude of, “This is how we do it now.” This motto means updating policies, SOPs, and guidelines to reflect the new practices. The University must deliver regular training refresher courses and use data to demonstrate the new improvements. The University can show people that the new system works by measuring error rates, turnaround times, and user satisfaction through surveys. The university community will no longer face uncertainties about paychecks or lost paperwork, allowing everyone to focus on teaching and serving students.

6. Future State

The benefits of digital transformations are diverse. The selected university will gain numerous benefits from this change. Some anticipated future outcomes are:

- A fully electronic ePAF system will reduce paper usage, eliminate redundancies, and streamline data flow from the departments to HR.
- Errors will be reduced, turnaround times will be quicker, and accuracy will be improved for payroll and reporting.
- A smooth and timely process for all personnel actions will be ensured. Overall, administrative process automation will speed up operations, decrease errors, and lessen workload, enhancing organizational efficiency.
- HR Specialists will transition to data review and quality control rather than data entry, increasing their strategic focus.
- Faculty and staff will have improved learning experiences by using digital tools that provide online collaboration.
- The university will gain a competitive advantage and long-term cost savings, reducing unnecessary manual labor.

7. Conclusion

Implementing Kotter’s 8-Step Model ensures the transition to a new electronic Personnel Action Form system is systematic and inclusive. By establishing urgency, building a dedicated guiding coalition, and communicating a clear vision, the university sets the stage for this change. Involving influencers and the Administration, highlighting short-term wins, and standardizing the new process will help solidify the change. Through monitoring and support, the faculty and staff can remain confident that the university’s HR and payroll processes will be accurate and reliable, and people can do their jobs without worrying about their pay or benefits.

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